

MULTISCALE ANALYSIS OF THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY FOR PARTICULATED NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Nanocomposites materials including the nanofillers which size is smaller than 100nm show abnormal properties such as multifunctionality due to the high surface to volume ratio of fillers. In addition, the surface to volume ratios of interface region are very sensitivity to the size of fillers, so the filler size is one of the effect factors to decide the effective properties of nanocomposites. So the size effect induced by filler size has been verified on various properties such as the elastic stiffness[1,2], the coefficient of thermal expansion[3] through various studies.

Kapitza resistance[4] which exists at interface between two different materials in heterogeneous materials affects thermal conductivity. It intercepts the heat flow at the interface, so the effective thermal conductivity of the whole material falls off. So the various studies have been performed to verify the weakened effect of reinforcing fillers due to the Kapitza resistance[5-6]. Especially in nanometer scales, together with the size effect of fillers, the Kapitza resistance plays a prominent part due to the larger surface to volume ratio of filler.

In this study, the size effects on the effective thermal conductivity induced by filler size and Kapitza resistance are verified through the non-equilibrium molecular dynamics (NEMD) simulations. And a sequential multiscale model based on the micromechanics is also developed for efficient analysis and design of nanocomposites.

2 Atomistic Analysis

2.1 Models

To characterize the particle size effect, we prepared a total of eight different molecular unit cells consist of epoxy chains and spherical silicon carbide (SiC) particles. The epoxy chain constructed with nine chains of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol F (EPON862[®]) and three chains of triethylenetetramine (TETA[®]) was used as matrix material. The eight different filler whose radii changed from 5.8 to 16 Å were used as the reinforcing filler. But the volume fraction of filler was fixed as 5.8% to restrict effect factors except the particle size. The details of unit cell are listed in table 1. For the isotropic unit cell, matrix was constructed as amorphous structure and the filler was inserted into the center of the cell.

2.2 NEMD Method

The cells were minimized to obtain the minimum potential energy through the conjugate gradient method. Then, the equilibrium process was applied

Table 1 Unit cell compositions

System	Radius (Å)	Cell length (Å)		Cell density (g/cm ³)
		X=Y	Z	
TC1	5.18	21.57	43.14	1.23
TC2	7.54	31.40	62.80	
TC3	9.00	37.32	74.64	
TC4	10.9	45.38	90.76	
TC5	11.6	48.41	96.82	
TC6	13.0	54.29	108.58	
TC7	14.0	58.19	116.38	
TC 8	16.0	66.63	133.26	

using NVT ensemble at 300 K. Then, to obtain thermal conductivity, the NEMD(non-equilibrium molecular dynamics) method was carried out using the microcanonical (NVE) ensemble. The thermal conductivity was obtained using the heat flux induced the temperature difference inside the unit cell. To make the temperature difference, the heat sink region and source region were defined. Then the same amount heat energy was added and removed from the defined regions. During the microcanonical ensemble, the cell became equilibrium state which the temperature gradient did not change in spite of continuous heat exchange. Then thermal conductivity was calculated using Fourier`s law as follows:

$$\lambda = -\frac{J_q}{dT/dz} \quad (1)$$

where heat flux, J_q is determined from the added or removed heat energy, ΔE and the cross-sectional area of unit cell, A_c as follows:

$$J_q = \frac{\Delta E}{2A_c} \quad (2)$$

dT/dz is the steady-state temperature gradient determined from a least squares approximation of the discrete temperatures inside the cell. The discrete temperatures of each part according to the heat flow direction were obtained using virial theorem.

Fig.1. Molecular models (a) Nanoparticle composites cell (b) Layered cell for Kapitza interface (c) Interface gap between epoxy and SiC.

2.3 NEMD method for Kapitza resistance

When the heterogeneous materials are made up, the vacant interface region between two different materials is generated due to the repulsive interaction between the materials. The heat is transferred by phonon movement through the mediums such as covalent bonds, so it is hardly transported from one material to the other one at interface due to the phonon reflection or scattering phenomenon appears in vacant region

In nanocomposites, the vacant region occupies the large portion of the total volume. So to consider and verify the Kapitza resistance is important. To verify the interface resistance(=Kapitza resistance), the layer model consists of epoxy and SiC was constructed as Fig 1(b). After modeling, the minimizing process was applied to obtain the minimum potential energy state using conjugate gradient method. During the minimizing process, the vacant interface region was generated due to the repulsive interface between epoxy and SiC layers. The thickness of the Kapitza interface region obtained from the averaged distance between epoxy surface and SiC surface through analysis of atomic coordinates is 2.18Å. Then, an abrupt temperature drop was appeared at interface due to the interface resistance when the NEMD method was applied to the model. From the temperature difference at interface, the thermal Kapitza resistance (thermal interface resistance) was obtained. These value, thermal interface resistance and interfacial thickness are intrinsic properties defined as the atomistic interaction, so they can be applied to the multiscale model for nanocomposites.

2.4 Results

To guarantee the accuracy of the result in spite of the variation of molecular dynamics, the NEMD simulation of each cell was performed three times repetitively and the averaged value over three different results was adopted as the final result.

Through comparing the thermal conductivities of nanocomposites systems to that of the pure epoxy, the reinforcing effect and the interface thermal resistance effect can be verified. The thermal conductivities and the interface volume fraction according to the systems (size of filler) are listed in table 2. Among the systems, TC1 and TC2 shows lower value than the pure epoxy system despite

including the reinforcing filler. These results were induced by the larger interface resistance due to the relative larger interface volume fraction.

3 Multiscale Analysis

In nanocomposites, the thickness and volume fraction of Kapitza and effective interfaces are not negligible. So a multi-inclusion model was adopted to describe the effective thermal conductivity of nanocomposites in the micromechanics regime.

3.1 Multi-inclusion model

In the multi-inclusion model of thermal conductivity, it is assumed that a multiple-layered inclusion is embedded into an infinite medium with undetermined thermal conductivity. The steady state effective thermal conductivity of nanocomposites \mathbf{K}_{comp} is given as

$$\mathbf{K}_{comp} = \mathbf{K}_{inf} : \left[\mathbf{I} + (\mathbf{S} - \mathbf{I}) : (f_p \Phi_p + f_K \Phi_K + f_i \Phi_i + f_m \Phi_m) \right] : \left[\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{S} : (f_p \Phi_p + f_K \Phi_K + f_i \Phi_i + f_m \Phi_m) \right]^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{K}_{inf} is the conductivity of an infinite medium. Φ_r is a ratio of the average eigen-temperature gradient of the r^{th} phase to the overall temperature gradient, given as

$$\Phi_r = \left[(\mathbf{K}_{inf} - \mathbf{K}_r)^{-1} : \mathbf{K}_{inf} - \mathbf{S} \right]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

Table 2 Thermal conductivities and interface properties results according to the particle size

System	TC (W/mK)	Interface volume ratio	Effective Interface		
			Thickness (Å)	Volume fraction	TC (W/mK)
TC1	0.1182	0.108	4.99	0.587	0.102
TC2	0.1376	0.066	4.63	0.292	0.093
TC3	0.1742	0.054	5.17	0.217	0.193
TC4	0.1844	0.042	4.47	0.157	0.268
TC5	0.1968	0.039	4.87	0.141	0.395
TC6	0.2132	0.034	5.54	0.118	0.751
TC7	0.1982	0.032	5.17	0.107	0.133
TC 8	0.2332	0.027	3.57	0.087	4.200
Epoxy	0.1416				-
SiC	120				-

f_r is the volume fraction of the r^{th} phase in which the subscripts p, K, i, and m correspond to the particle, Kapitza interface, effective interface, and matrix, respectively.

3.2 Effective interface properties

The thickness and volume fraction of the effective interface are determined through the analysis of radial density distribution. After the volume fraction of the effective interface is determined, the thermal conductivity of the effective interface can be directly obtained from the Eq. (3). Because the effective thermal conductivity given in the Eq. (3) is a closed form solution, it can be easily rearranged with respect to the undetermined thermal conductivity of the effective interface given as:

$$\mathbf{K}_i = \mathbf{K}_{inf}^{-1} \left\{ \mathbf{I} - \left[f_i \mathbf{B}^{-1} (\mathbf{K}_{inf}^{-1} \mathbf{K}_{comp} \mathbf{S} - \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{I}) + \mathbf{S} \right]^{-1} \right\} \quad (5)$$

3.3 Results

The thickness and the thermal conductivity of the effective interface are arranged in Table2. The thermal conductivity of the interface clearly shows the particle size dependency. In order to describe the particle-size effect on the thermal conductivity at various compositions, the thermal conductivity of the effective interface was fitted into a function of the particle radius in the unit of W/mK as, $K_{int} = 0.009 \exp(0.3493r_p)$ using a least square approximation. Then, the contribution of the Kapitza resistance and effective interface required to characterize the effective thermal conductivity of the nanocomposites is prepared and the Eqs. (3-4) can be used to estimate the effective thermal conductivity at various particle radius and volume fractions. The thermal conductivity obtained from the present bridging method is compared with the MD simulation results and the Mori-Tanaka estimations in Fig. 2. The present micromechanics-based multiscale model efficiently reproduced the MD simulations results with reliable accuracy.

Fig.2. Thermal conductivities obtained from molecular dynamics, micromechanics and bridging method.

4 Result

In this study, the size effect on thermal conductivity was verified through molecular dynamics simulation. In the results, the two cases which include the smallest particle have smaller value than the pure epoxy due to the Kapitza resistance effect. Then thermal conductivities increased depending on the particle size and shows higher values than thermal conductivity of pure epoxy due to the enhanced effect of effective interface. And the sequential multiscale method was developed to represent the size effect appeared in the result of atomistic analysis. The proposed method shows corresponding result with atomistic analysis and can efficiently estimate the thermal conductivity including the size effect.

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